

A THERMOCHEMICAL STUDY ON THE PRIMARY OXIDATION OF SULFUR

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Abstract

Several chemical reactions related to the oxidation and combustion of sulfur are investigated using a number of computational chemistry methods with the objective of determining appropriate methods for use in developing an elementary reaction mechanism for oxidation of sulfur. Calculations are focused on thermochemical properties and reaction energetics for reactive species and transition state structures for reactions in the oxidation / combustion of sulfur. Reactions involving several intermediates resulting from the reactions of S_2 with oxygen were investigated with the density functional theory B3LYP (with several basis sets) and BB1K/GTLarge. The composite ab-initio methods G2, G3, G3MP2, G3B3, G3MP2B3 and CBS-QB3 were also used. Enthalpies of a series of sulfur compounds and transition state structures are calculated using the ab initio and DFT calculations. The calculations were combined with isodesmic reaction analysis, whenever possible, in order to cancel error and improve the accuracy of the calculations. Results show that all B3LYP DFT calculations including the 6-311++G(3df,2p) basis set show poor outcome in estimating the enthalpy of reactions involving S_2 . The six composite methods have all shown consistency with each other and their calculated reaction energies / bond energies are in good agreement with the available literature. Kinetic parameters for calculation of the kinetic parameters on SO_3 dissociation to SO_2 and O using the canonical transition state theory are reported.

Introduction

Combustion of elemental sulfur is performed in large-scale as a part of the industrial production process of sulfuric acid which is one of the world's largest-volume industrial chemicals. As such, sulfur combustion in existing facilities is technically robust and mostly designed to realize large product streams [1, 2]. Electricity generation may be carried out with the heat generated from sulfur combustion and the process is independent of encasement: Sulfur is a very cost-effective material and can be inexpensively stored outdoor under ambient conditions for long times and in large quantities [2]. In contrast, there has been relatively little research on the combustion of elemental sulfur.

Several studies have focused on the oxidation of SO_2 to SO_3 . Naidoo et al. have conducted an experimental kinetic study of the $SO_2 + O$ association [3] and Jiang et al. have reported a quantum chemistry study on the reaction of SO_2 with O_3 and H_2O_2 [4]. The reactions of diatomic sulfur S_2 in the atmosphere with O, O_2 and O_3 and HO_2 have been investigated in the experimental work of Hills et al. [5] and rates of some reactions have been determined. Little data on the kinetics of SO_3 dissociation and sulfur combustion are available. Yilmaz et al. [6] have conducted experiments on the thermal dissociation of SO_3 in the temperature range of 1000-1400 K and have determined a rate constant for $SO_3 + N_2 \rightarrow SO_2 + O + N_2$.

The main purpose of the present work is to compile, test and validate the performance of one or several computational methods to provide accurate results for the thermochemical properties of reactions and rate coefficients of the combustion of elemental sulfur. A further

goal is to develop a detailed reaction mechanism for the reactions of the $S_2 + O_2$ system on the basis of elementary reactions. We compare also quantum chemistry based calculations with the experimental values of Yilmaz et al. [6].

Computational Methods

Thermochemical and kinetic properties for sulfur compounds (stable molecules, radicals and transition state structures) are calculated with the help of several computational methods using the Gaussian 03 program suite [7, 8]. Hybrid density functional theory (DFT) methods are used with B3LYP/6-311G(d,p), B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p), B3LYP/6-311+G(2d, p), B3LYP/6-311++G(3df, 2p), B3LYP/CBSB7 [9, 10, 11] basis sets. The hybrid Hartree-Fock-density functional model called the Becke88-Becke95 1-parameter model for kinetics BB1K/GTLarge [12, 13] is also evaluated. Six composite methods (ab-initio) are tested and used in this work (G2 [14], G3 [15], G3 theory performs a sequence of ab initio molecular orbital calculations selected to remove errors) and further calibrated to yield an accurate total energy for a species. Optimized structures and frequencies are obtained at the Hartree-Fock HF/6-31G(d) level and G3MP2 [16]. The modified G3 theory using B3LYP geometries was employed and referred as G3MP2B3 [10, 9] and G3B3. These last two methods use geometries and zero-point energies at the B3LYP/6-31G(d) level. Finally, the well-regarded CBS-QB3 [17] is also examined for use in the sulfur / oxygen system.

Results and Discussion

Validation of methods with known enthalpy values for sulfur compound

Enthalpy of formation

Geometries and standard enthalpies of formation of some reactants, products and transition state structures describing the primary reactions for the combustion of sulfur are reported. In order to find accurate computational methods, DFT methods at several levels and composite ab-initio methods are used. Standard enthalpies are calculated using different isodesmic reactions (hypothetical reactions with similarity in mass and bonding environments for reactant and product sets in order to provide cancellation of systematic errors). Transition state structure (TS) enthalpies were obtained from the computational energy of the TS structure relative to both the reactants and products. Zero-point energies (ZPVEs) and thermal corrections to 298.15 K are applied for all calculations. Frequencies and moments of inertia are obtained from each method in order to calculate the entropies and heat capacities. The latter results are not reported in this study.

Tables 1 and 2 list the calculated enthalpy of formation (kcal mol^{-1}) for SO, SO_2 , SO_3 and SSO along with literature values for comparison. Table 1 reports the calculated values from six composite ab-initio methods (CBS-QB3, G2, G3, G3MP2, G3B3 and G3MP2B3), while in Table 2, a series of DFT calculations at six levels (B3LYP at different basis sets and BB1K) are listed. The enthalpies, $\Delta_f H_{298}^0$, listed in Table 1 show very good agreement with the literature values and precision through the different work reactions.

The spin value (singlet, triplet) is of crucial importance in the calculation of the energy and consequently in the determination of the thermodynamics and kinetics. We note a deviation of 1 to 4 kcal mol^{-1} among the composite methods and the literature values.

All of the DFT calculations gave poor outcome for the calculation of enthalpies of these sulfur species at all basis levels, while the calculation of the structure parameters (lengths, angles, dihedrals) is in good agreement with literature data [18, 19, 20]. It appears that, for oxygenated sulfur compounds, DFT is not eligible. Therefore, for further investigations in

developing an elementary reaction mechanism for oxidation of sulfur, the six composite methods are selected and will be used.

Table 1. Enthalpy of formation for species resulting from several sulfur / oxygen systems calculated at CBS-QB3, G2, G3, G3B3, G3MP2 and G3MP2B3 levels (in kcal mol⁻¹)

Structure	Reactions	$\Delta_f H_{298}^0$ in kcal mol ⁻¹					
		CBS-QB3	G2	G3	G3B3	G3MP2	G3MP2B3
	SO → ³ S + ³ O NIST = 1.2	-1.23	1.86	0.44	0.20	1.02	0.47
	SO ₂ + ³ O → SO ₃ SO ₃ → SO + ³ O ₂ SO ₃ → ³ S + ³ O + ³ O ₂ ³ S ₂ + 3 ³ O ₂ → 2SO ₃ NIST = -94.59	-94.22 -92.53 -93.41 -92.40 -93.14	-93.45 -96.33 -94.11 -96.10 -95.00	-93.12 -91.06 -90.27 -91.53 -91.50	-92.61 -90.39 -89.84 -90.60 -90.86	-92.02 -91.32 -89.95 -90.97 -91.07	-91.72 -90.28 -89.46 -89.61 -90.27
	2 ³ SO + ³ O ₂ → 2SO ₂ ³ S + O ₂ ³ → SO ₂ ³ S ₂ + 2 ³ O ₂ → 2SO ₂ NIST = -70.939	-69.55 -70.13 -69.42 -69.70	-72.66 -71.60 -72.44 -72.23	-68.20 -68.09 -68.67 -68.32	-68.64 -68.17 -68.86 -68.56	-69.11 -68.87 -68.76 -68.91	-69.17 -68.68 -68.50 -68.78
	³ SSO → ³ O + ³ S ₂ ³ SSO → ³ S + ³ SO NIST = -13.50	-13.17 -12.16 -12.67	-15.72 -14.72 -15.22	-12.16 -10.23 -11.19	-12.86 -10.49 -11.68	-12.15 -12.19 -12.17	-12.79 -12.42 -12.60

Table 2. Enthalpy of formation for species resulting from several sulfur / oxygen systems with the DFT methods, B3LYP and BB1K and indicated basis sets (in kcal mol⁻¹)

Structure	Reactions	$\Delta_f H_{298}^0$ in kcal mol ⁻¹					
		B3LYP/6-311G(d,p)	B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p)	B3LYP/6-311+G(2d,p)	B3LYP/6-311++G(3df,2p)	B3LYP/CBSB7	BB1K/GTlarge
	³ SO → ³ S + ³ O NIST = 1.2	12.96	11.32	4.90	0.13	8.08	-7.21
	SO ₂ + ³ O → SO ₃ SO ₃ → SO + ³ O ₂ SO ₃ → ³ S + ³ O + ³ O ₂ ³ S ₂ + 3 ³ O ₂ → 2SO ₃ NIST = -94.59	-73.46 -75.10 -32.76 -38.78 -55.03	-70.33 -71.73 -31.72 -37.71 -52.88	-79.57 -89.71 -55.96 -57.87 -70.78	-87.27 -74.29 -73.81 -73.17 -77.13	-81.39 -91.96 -54.50 -56.77 -71.15	-85.03 -81.35 -61.86 -49.70 -69.48
	2SO ₃ + ³ O ₂ → 2SO ₂ ³ S + ³ O ₂ → SO ₂ S ²⁺ + 2O ₂ ³⁻ → 2SO ₂ NIST = -70.939	-43.00 -30.24 -35.71 -36.32	-42.41 -32.33 -36.73 -37.16	-52.22 -47.33 -48.88 -49.48	-58.56 -57.48 -57.44 -57.83	-51.93 -44.05 -45.77 -47.25	-50.11 -47.77 -44.81 -47.56
	³ SSO → ³ O + ³ S ₂ ³ SSO → ³ S + SO NIST = -13.50	-11.29 -18.54 -14.91	-12.07 -19.02 -15.54	-21.50 -27.88 -24.69	-4.53 -3.54 -4.04	-18.72 -28.55 -23.64	-30.48 -33.27 -31.87

Bond energy calculations

The dissociation reaction of SO₃ to SO₂ + O assimilated to S—O bond energy (BE) in the SO₃ molecule has been determined at different levels of calculation (DFT and ab-initio). For each method, the bond energy is estimated as the calculated energy difference between the products and adducts and converted into kcal mol⁻¹. The BE values are listed in Table 3. According to reported enthalpies in the literature [21], the S—O bond energy is calculated to be 83.20 kcal mol⁻¹. The different B3LYP methods listed in Table 3 yield lower BE values (62-75 kcal mol⁻¹) while all six composite methods calculations (G2, G3, G3MP2, G3B3, G3MP2B3 and CBS-QB3) are near 81-83 kcal mol⁻¹ which is in very good agreement with the

literature. We note a deviation of only 0.4 and 1.1 kcal mol⁻¹ between CBS-QB3 and G2 value from literature.

Table 3. S—O Bond energy in SO₃ in kcal mol⁻¹.

$SO_3 \rightarrow SO_2 + O$ Literature = 83.20 [21]			
Method-basis set	BE (kcal mol ⁻¹)	Method-basis set	BE (kcal mol ⁻¹)
B3LYP/6-311G(d,p)	62.07	CBS-QB3	82.83
B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p)	58.94	G2	82.06
B3LYP/6-311G+(2d,p)	68.18	G3	81.73
B3LYP/6-311G++(3df,2p)	75.88	G3B3	81.22
B3LYP/CBSB7	70.0	G3MP2	80.63
BB1K	73.64	G3MP2B3	80.34

The S—O bond energy (BE) in the SO₂ molecule has been also determined at different levels of calculation (DFT and ab-initio) and is listed in Table 4. Based on enthalpies reported in the literature [21], the S—O bond energy in SO₂ is calculated to be strong with 130.14 kcal mol⁻¹. As above, all B3LYP methods yield lower BE values (103-120 kcal mol⁻¹) while all six composite methods calculations are very similar by 130-138 kcal mol⁻¹. We note a difference of less than 1 kcal mol⁻¹ between CBS-QB3, G3B3, G3MP2B3 and literature.

Table 4. S—O Bond energy in SO₂ in kcal mol⁻¹.

$SO_2 \rightarrow SO + O$ Literature = 130.14 [21]			
Method-basis set	BE (kcal mol ⁻¹)	Method-basis set	BE (kcal mol ⁻¹)
B3LYP/6-311G(d,p)	103.2	CBS-QB3	130.61
B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p)	101.57	G2	132.26
B3LYP/6-311G+(2d,p)	112.61	G3	128.28
B3LYP/6-311G++(3df,2p)	119.9	G3B3	129.32
B3LYP/CBSB7	112.13	G3MP2	138.73
BB1K	120.06	G3MP2B3	129.59

The third molecule tested for the validation of the methods is SSO, with two different bonds, S—O (at 102.24 kcal mol⁻¹) and S—S (at 80.95 kcal mol⁻¹). The S—O bond is stronger by some 22 kcal mol⁻¹ than S—S. We also note that S—O (in SSO) is stronger by 19 kcal mol⁻¹ than in SO₃ but weaker by 28 kcal mol⁻¹ than in SO₂. The calculated S—S and S—O BE using the same methods and listed in Table 5 confirm the above observations, namely that DFT is not eligible for oxygenated sulfur compounds.

Table 5. S—O and S—S bond energies in SSO in kcal mol⁻¹.

${}^3SSO \rightarrow {}^2SS + {}^3O / {}^3SSO \rightarrow {}^3S + {}^3SO$ Literature = 102.24 / 80.95 [21]					
Method-basis set	BE (kcal mol ⁻¹)		Method-basis set	BE (kcal mol ⁻¹)	
	S—O	S—S		S—O	S—S
B3LYP/6-311G(d,p)	77.43	56.95	CBS-QB3	101.91	79.61
B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p)	78.09	58.12	G2	104.46	82.16
B3LYP/6-311G+(2d,p)	87.52	66.83	G3	100.89	77.67
B3LYP/6-311G++(3df,2p)	93.27	70.99	G3B3	101.6	77.93
B3LYP/CBSB7	84.82	66.97	G3MP2	100.88	79.63
BB1K	98.15	74.76	G3MP2B3	101.52	79.86

Calculations for other species involved in sulfur oxidation

Enthalpy of formation of stable species and enthalpies of transition state structures

Table 6 illustrates structures and lists the calculated standard enthalpies of formation of four species. All calculated enthalpies show very good agreement throughout the six composite methods. A second structure for SO₃ (Table 6) has been observed. The structure is non planar, one S=O double bond can be seen at 1.47 Å and two S—O single bonds at 1.63 Å. This structure is stable but the corresponding enthalpy is significantly higher with 64 kcal mol⁻¹ at -30.71 kcal mol⁻¹ (at CBS-QB3 level). This structure might come into play in building of a reaction mechanism.

There are also two calculated geometries for SSO, one structure is bent as illustrated in Table 1 and one is linear as illustrated in Table 6. The calculated enthalpy of the linear form of SSO is much higher with 26.77 kcal mol⁻¹ versus -12.67 kcal mol⁻¹ for the bent form (both at CBS-QB3 level). This higher energy geometry is not used in the present work but should be also considered in the elaboration of a mechanism. A new stable species, SS(=O)=O, with consistent enthalpy value among the different methods is calculated and reported in Table 6.

Table 6. Enthalpy of formation for species resulting from several sulfur / oxygen systems calculated at CBS-QB3, G2, G3, G3B3, G3MP2 and G3MP2B3 levels (in kcal mol⁻¹).

Structure	Reactions	$\Delta_f H_{298}^0$ in kcal mol ⁻¹					
		CBS-QB3	G2	G3	G3B3	G3MP2	G3MP2B3
	SO ₂ + ³ O → SO ₃	-31.79	-32.33	-31.24	-30.32	-30.57	-29.89
	SO ₃ → ³ SO + ³ O ₂	-30.10	-35.21	-29.18	-28.09	-29.87	-28.45
	SO ₃ → ³ S + O ³ + ³ O ₂	-30.98	-32.99	-28.39	-27.55	-28.50	-27.63
	2SO ₃ → ³ S ₂ + 3 ³ O ₂	-29.97	-34.98	-29.66	-28.31	-29.52	-27.78
	Average	-30.71	-33.88	-29.62	-28.57	-29.62	-28.44
	SOO → ³ O ₂ + ³ S	47.54	42.80	46.25	47.42	46.76	47.78
	SOO → ³ SO + ³ O	46.27	41.35	45.26	45.47	46.10	46.07
	Average	46.90	42.08	45.76	46.44	46.43	46.92
	³ SSO-L → ³ O + ³ S ₂	26.26	25.66	26.46	26.36	26.96	26.09
	³ SSO-L → ³ S + ³ SO	27.27	26.66	28.39	28.73	26.92	26.46
	Average	26.77	26.16	27.43	27.55	26.94	26.27
	SS(=O)=O → SO ₂ + S ³	-42.39	-41.59	-41.22	-40.10	-41.39	-40.60
	SS(=O)=O → SSO + O ³	-44.19	-42.50	-42.63	-42.29	-41.29	-41.14
	Average	-43.29	-42.05	-41.92	-41.20	-41.34	-40.87

Table 7 illustrates seven transition state structures determined at the six composite levels. Transition state structures have been identified for both SO₃ geometries. The TSO₃-A structure results from the planer SO₃ and clearly shows one oxygen atom leaving the SO₃ molecule, as illustrated in Figure 1 (left). This structure also shows two S=O double bonds, while the third S—O at 2.02 Å has the oxygen leaving the sulfur atom. The calculated enthalpy values for this TSO₃-A are in agreement with each other.

Figure 1: Left: Structure of TS-SO₃-A at CBS-QB3, G2, G3 and G3MP2.

Right: Structure of TS-SO₃-B at CBS-QB3, G3B3 and G3MP2B3.

The transition state structure of the non-planar SO₃ (TSO₃-B) is illustrated in Figure 1 (right). The vibrations show oxygens 2 and 3 moving to form a new O—O bond and SO plus O₂. This structure has been obtained with the CBS-QB3, G3B3 and G3MP2B3 methods at enthalpy values of -8.39, -3.76 and -3.31 kcal mol⁻¹, respectively. The three other methods (G2, G3, G3MP2) appear to convert the molecule to the TSO₃-A structure and suggest that only B3LYP geometries calculations (if this study) identify TSO₃-B.

Table 7. Enthalpies for transition state structures from sulfur / oxygen systems calculated at CBS-QB3, G2, G3, G3B3, G3MP2 and G3MP2B3 levels (in kcal mol⁻¹). The listed two values give the enthalpies of the TS structures calculated relative to both the reactants and products.

Structure	Reactions	$\Delta H_{TS(298)}$ in kcal mol ⁻¹					
		CBS-QB3	G2	G3	G3B3	G3MP2	G3MP2B3
	SO ₂ + ³ O → TSO ₃ -A TSO ₃ -A → SO ₃ Average	-17.37 -16.19 -16.78	-11.58 -11.17 -11.38	-14.77 -14.69 -14.73	Fails	-14.09 -15.11 -14.60	Fails
	SO ₂ + ³ O → TSO ₃ -B TSO ₃ -B → SO ₃ Average	-7.80 -8.98 -8.39	Fails	Fails	-3.98 -3.54 -3.76	Fails	-3.97 -2.65 -3.31
	SSO → TOS-S TOS-S → ³ S + ³ SO Average	65.60 66.94 66.27				61.79 63.10 62.45	62.17 63.26 62.71
	SSO → TSS-O TSS-O → ³ S ₂ + ³ O Average	Fails	83.71 81.49 82.60	80.20 81.55 80.88	Fails	88.55 89.90 89.90	Fails
	SO + O → TSOO TSOO → SOO Average	138.56 137.92 138.24			119.82 118.85 119.34		130.53 129.67 130.10
	SOO → TSO ₂ TSO ₂ → SO ₂ Average	120.04 119.87 119.96	126.10 127.49 126.79	127.90 125.55 126.73	116.71 114.92 115.81	128.05 126.31 127.18	117.88 116.47 117.17
	SS(=O)(=O) → TS TS → SO ₂ + ³ O Average	20.77 21.68 21.23	22.05 22.51 22.28	20.68 21.39 21.03	19.93 21.03 20.48	21.90 21.85 21.87	21.08 21.35 21.21

SSO (S₂O) can undergo dissociation by splitting the S—O or the S—S bonds. These dissociations are, however, high energetic and difficult to find with all methods. Only the G3MP2 level could find the cleavage of the S—S bond clearly. CBS-QB3 and G3MP2B3 showed a sort of “umbrella” transition state. Despite the different transition state structure, CBS-QB3 and G3MP2B3 enthalpy values are in agreement with that of G3MP2 structure. The O—O in SSO needs higher energy to cleave than the S—O. For these reactions, only the MP2 calculations could “identify” a transition state structure, namely G2, G3 and G3MP2. In some cases, calculations with MP2 make sequential reactions as observed in a previous work [22].

An interesting transition state (TSOO) resulting from the SO + O association was identified with the six methods. The resulting enthalpy value for these structures varies within the

methods. The methods using B3LYP for the optimization of geometries, CBS-QB3, G3B3 and G3MP2B3 have calculated imaginary frequency of -943.4, -908.3 and -908.3 cm^{-1} , respectively. The three other composite methods, G2, G3 and G3MP2B3, estimated the imaginary frequency at -1026.66 cm^{-1} . Comparison of the O-O and S-O distances in these two set of methods show that all O-O and S-O distances are shorter than those from methods involving MP2 calculations. Similar results are obtained with the TSO₂ transition state structure. The group CBS-QB3, G3B3 and G3MP2B3 methods calculated an imaginary frequency at -827.4, -861.9 and -861.9 respectively, versus -270.5 for the group G2, G3 and G3MP2. The O-O distance with the first set of methods is significantly shorter with 1.94 Å versus 2.46 Å. The enthalpy value for this transition state is likely to be about 116-119 kcal mol⁻¹.

Reaction of SO₂ + O^{3p} to SO₃: potential diagram and kinetics

Potentials for SO₂ + O^{3p} → SO₃

Figure 2, illustrates the formation of SO₃ from SO₂ + ³O association. On the left, we can see that the more stable planar form of SO₃ is highly exothermic with some 80 kcal mol⁻¹ and the association occurs without barrier. On the right side of Figure 2, formation of the non-planar SO₃ is also exothermic but to a much lower extent with some 20 kcal mol⁻¹. For this SO₃-B transition state structure a small barrier is required.

Figure 2: Left: Structure of TS-SO₃-A at CBS-QB3, G2, G3 and G3MP2. Right: Structure of TS-SO₃-B at CBS-QB3, G3B3 and G3MP2B3.

Kinetic calculations for SO₃ → SO₂ + O^{3p}

The reaction of SO₃ to SO₂ can also occur under catalytic conditions [6]. The decomposition of SO₃ is a slow but important reaction and can serve to control the O₂ concentration in the SO₃-H₂O decomposition system [23]. The kinetic parameters for the dissociation of the two structures of SO₃ have been evaluated with the results of the composite methods.

The reaction rate constants for this unimolecular dissociation reaction have been calculated on the basis of the canonical transition state theory [24] and are listed in Table 8 along with the results of Yilmaz et al. [6] and Zhang et al. [23]. Good agreement can be seen within the composite methods. The activation energy for TS-SO₃ planar (TSO3-A) is close to that determined by Zhang et al. [23]. The structure TS-SO₃-B results in a lower activation energy.

The low activation energies from the experiments in the literature compared with the calculated ones indicate that the reactions could be more complex and consist of sequential reactions.

Table 8: Kinetic parameters for the reaction $\text{SO}_3 \rightarrow \text{SO}_2 + \text{O}$ in CHEMKIN format

$k = A T^n \exp(-E/RT)$			
Methods	A	n	Ea
Kinetic parameters for TS-SO3-A Planar			
CBS-QB3	4.5143E+13	0.655	76738
G2	5.9034E+10	1.343	83960
G3	1.0020E+12	0.841	77062
G3MP2	1.0020E+12	0.841	76762
Kinetic parameters for TS-SO3-B non-planar			
CBS-QB3	1.0216E+12	0.337	22766
G3B3	3.7368E+12	0.156	25370
G3MP2B3	5.6091E+12	0.156	25690
Kinetic parameters from literature			
Yilmaz et al. [6]	5.70E-17	-	40000
Zhang et al. [23]	3.16E+15	-	63390

AT^n ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1}$), Ea (cal mol^{-1})

Reactions of SSO and SO_2

Potentials for ${}^3\text{SSO} \rightarrow {}^3\text{S}_2 + {}^3\text{O}$ and $\text{SSO} \rightarrow {}^3\text{SO} + {}^3\text{S}$

Reaction enthalpies of SSO relative to the transition state structures TSS-O and TSO-S have been calculated at different levels as listed in Table 7. As illustrated in Figure 3, the oxygen atom cleavage is endothermic by approximately $100 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ but the oxygen atom leaves without a significant added barrier. This is similar to reactions of oxygenated hydrocarbons [19]. The transition state structure for the dissociation of the sulfur atom from SSO is also difficult to identify. At G3MP2 level, the transition state structure needs near 76 kcal mol^{-1} , relative to SSO, and a barrier of near 13 kcal mol^{-1} , relative to the set of products $\text{SO} + \text{S}$, can be seen.

Potentials for ${}^3\text{S}_2 + {}^3\text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{SS}(=\text{O})=\text{O} \rightarrow \text{SO}_2 + {}^3\text{S}$

There are several reaction paths for the formation of SO_2 reported in the literature [3, 25, 26]. In the present work we report two new paths calculated at the CBS-QB3 level. The first one (TS1 in Figure 4) is obtained from the association of ${}^3\text{S}_2 + {}^3\text{O}_2$. In TS1, an oxygen is bonded to one sulfur atom, forming SSOO expected to occur without barrier. The exact structure of the SSOO needs to be thoroughly investigated and requires new calculations in a future study. TS1 illustrated in Figure 4 shows the intramolecular abstraction of the peroxy oxygen atom to the middle sulfur atom and form a stable $\text{SS}(=\text{O})=\text{O}$ at $-43 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ (see Figures 4). CBS-QB3 calculations show clearly the displacement of the oxygen toward the sulfur atom. The subsequent reaction of the new formed molecule ($\text{SS}(=\text{O})=\text{O}$) reacts further by cleaving one

sulfur atom to form SO_2 and S over about 65 kcal mol^{-1} energy barrier. This reaction is possible looking at the S—S bond energy in SS(=O)=O of $38.6 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ which is weak compared with the S—S bond in S_2 of $102 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$. It is important to point out that the ${}^3\text{S}_2 + {}^3\text{O}_2$, which is a complicated association, leads to the formation of different products and undergoes different transition state structures depending on the structure of the intermediate S_2O_2 formed. This investigation will be reported in a future work.

Figure 3: Dissociation of SSO to $\text{S}_2 + \text{O}$ and $\text{SO} + \text{S}$

Figure 4: Formation of SO_2 from $\text{S}_2 + \text{O}_2$ association

Potentials for ${}^3\text{SO} + {}^3\text{O} \rightarrow \text{SOO} \rightarrow \text{SO}_2$

The association of ${}^3\text{SO} + \text{O}$ has shown an interesting transition state structure (see Figure 5 and Table 7) calculated with the six composite methods. TS1 in Figure 5 shows clearly the migration of one triplet oxygen atom towards the SO molecule over 62 kcal mol^{-1} (at G3B3 level) relative to the entrance channel and form SOO at lower energy.

The six composite calculations have shown that the most favourable structure is bending the SOO moiety as illustrated in Figure 5 and listed in Table 6. Without consideration of the barrier, only a little overall energy (12 kcal mol^{-1}) is released during formation of the SOO .

The SOO^\ddagger formed at TS1, however has sufficient energy to pass over TS2 to form the more stable SO_2 by undergoing an intramolecular rearrangement.

The terminal oxygen undergoes an intramolecular abstraction (TS2 in Figure 5) and shifts to the sulfur atom to form the low energy SO_2 at about $-69 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$. This isomerization was found to have a barrier of 70 kcal mol^{-1} (at G3B3 level) relative to SOO .

Figure 5: Formation of SO_2 from $\text{SO} + \text{O}$ association

Table 9 reports the known literature values for sulfur compounds for use in theisodesmic reactions and for comparison with own calculations.

Table 9. Standard enthalpies used in this work

Literature standard enthalpy in kcal mol^{-1}	
S_2	30.736 ± 0.072 [27]
SO_2	-70.939 ± 0.048 [28]
SO_3	-94.591 [28]
SO	1.20 [28]
S	66.245 ± 0.036 [28]
SSO	-13.50 [28]

Conclusions

One objective of this work is to find an appropriate computational method for use in calculating of reaction parameters needed to develop a reaction mechanism for the oxidation of S_2 . A series of B3LYP DFT calculations with the basis sets 6-311G(d,p), 6-311+G(d,p), 6-311+G(2d,p), 6-311++G(3df,2p), CBSB7 as well as BB1K/GTLarge brought about poor results in predicting the thermochemistry of SO , SO_2 , SO_3 and SSO . Results from six composite methods, G2, G3, G3B3, G3MP2, G3MP2B3 and CBS-QB3 gave good agreement with literature data.

The results have shown that DFT with the basis sets used in this study is not eligible for oxygenated sulfur compounds but all composite ab-initio levels used in this work (several using DFT structures) yield reasonably good results. It also appears that CBS-QB3 and G3MP2B3 yield the best results. This needs to be further elaborated by extending the calculations to a larger number of species. Some kinetic data is reported in this work and some new transition state structures have been identified.

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